

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

BRAZILIAN ARMY AND THE ASTROS PROGRAM: DISRUPTIVE INNOVATION AND DOCTRINE FORMULATION.

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POLICY STATEMENT

In the history of warfare, the emergence of weapon systems with innovative technologies is known to promote changes in the Armed Forces. Beyond this process, such devices also function as catalysts for new perceptions within the military on the conduct of war, the ways of achieving victory, logistics options, and more. This policy brief aims to explore the relationship between technological innovation - in the form of disruptive technology - and doctrine change. Thus, we seek to analyze the AVTM-300 Tactical Cruise Missile (TCM), within the Astros 2020 Program, as an element of disruptive innovation, evaluating its implications for Brazilian Army doctrine formulation.

BACKGROUND

According to Wladimir Longo (2007, p.118), technological innovation is “the solution to a problem, technological, used for the first time, comprising the introduction of a new product or process in the market on a commercial scale [...]”. Not every innovation, however, can be considered disruptive. For that, it is necessary the existence of a “technological leap”, with changes in the “characteristics of the productive sectors in which they are used (for example: the laser, the transistor)” (LONGO, 2007, p.118). Thus, disruptive technological innovations are those that change the way war is made, i.e., cause an alteration in the way of fighting (PIERCE, 2004; ROSEN, 1991).

In the aftermath, they imply a change in Military Doctrine, understood here as the way to use the Force. According to Scott Sagan (2000, p.16-17), the doctrine defines under what conditions (when), with what purpose (why) and in what way (how) the Force will be used. Saint-Pierre and Gonçalves (2018) note that the impacts of a technological innovation on warfare will only be observed if there are adjustments in doctrine and military organization. That is: “[...] the mere presence of a new military artifact, or one of civilian origin with potential military employment, in an armed organization would not make it per se modern. In fact, there also needs to be, together, the coherent development of a new operational doctrine and an adequate organization to give it a really efficient employment” (SAINT-PIERRE, GONÇALVES, 2018, p. 29).

FINDINGS

The Astros (Artillery Saturation Rocket System) is a multiple rocket launcher (MRLS) for area saturation that began to be developed in the 1980s by the Brazilian Army and Avibrás. The system has already been tested in combat – in the Iran-Iraq War (1980) and in both Gulf Wars (1991 and 2003) – and is considered one of the best MRLS in the world. The Astros II is the system's evolution to the digital age, with a computerized firing unit. The Astros 2020 Program foresees, besides the SS-40G guided rocket, the development and production of a Tactical Cruise Missile (TCM), the AVTM-300 with a range of up to 300 km (AMARANTE, 2013; BRASIL, 2015). The Program also includes: (i) the construction of Santa Bárbara Fort (Formosa/GO), the physical base of the Missile and Rocket Artillery; and (ii) the deployment of the Army Artillery Command in Santa Bárbara Fort (BRASIL, 2019).

It is precisely the Tactical Cruise Missile that carries the potential for disruptive innovation. This is because, currently, the Brazilian Army does not have a doctrine for the use of this type of missile. The reference document, at the moment, is the "Doctrine Coordination Note No. 03/2015: Long Range Missile and Rocket Artillery Employment," published by the Army Doctrine Center (BRASIL, 2015). However, the text of the Note itself warns: "Until the doctrinal aspects established in this NCD have been incorporated into new Land Military Doctrine (DMT) manuals, they will be used only as a reference for experimentation, in school environments and in Land Force training exercises" (BRASIL, 2015, p.14).

A major aspect in relation to the use of the new Astros System is its subordination and chain of command. The Note No. 03/2015 states that, within the Theater of Operations (TO), the tactical cruise missile employment unit must be the Missile and Rocket Group (Grupo de Mísseis e Foguetes - GMF), composed of three Batteries (Bia MF). The GMF, in turn, is subordinated, in the beginning, to the Component Land Force (Força Terrestre Componente - FTC), integrating the FTC Artillery Command (BRASIL, 2015).

However, authors Dias and Gomes (2017) argue that the TCM could be subordinated directly to the Theater of Operations Commander, through a TO Artillery Command. The first reason given by the authors is that "the Astros system requires great coordination for fire backup and for the use of airspace [...]" (DIAS, GOMES, 2017, p. 126). Thus, if there were an Artillery Command subordinated to the TO Command itself, this coordination would occur within the Joint Staff meetings, specifically in the Fires Coordination Meeting and the Airspace Coordination Meeting.

This assessment and recommendation by the authors stem from the fact that the TCM is not just a tactical fire support armament (traditional Artillery mission), but rather lends itself to operational and even strategic level missions. As stated in the Note:

"The GMF has the mission of conducting fires against tactical, operational and even strategic targets [...]. It normally fires on strategic structures, gravity centers, or large and long-range targets, according to its vocation for area saturation.

The main targets indicated for TCM are command and control (C2) facilities, logistics bases, large unit area, enemy aviation bases, in addition to those of great strategic value or high military importance." [...] The ASTROS system also

participates in coastal defense operations, especially in operations against amphibious landing” (BRASIL, 2015, p.5, 7, 8).

In this case, the unit responsible for decisions on operational and strategic targets is the one at the highest level - regarding Joint Operations, the responsibility lies with the Theater of Operations Command. Therefore, the authors consider it more congruent to think of its use directly subordinated to this Command, and as an exception, subordinated to the FTC (DIAS, GOMES, 2017). In the words of Dias and Gomes (2017, p.142): “it makes the option of subordinating the Astros 2020, equipped with TCM, to the FTC more complex, less efficient, faster and safer. [...] After all, the more degrees of coordination required, the more limited the employment of the TCM will be”.

It is possible to realize that the employment of the TCM requires coordination both between the Forces (at least between the Land Force and the Air Force) and with other Armed Forces and services of the Land Force - for example, with the Army's Remotely Piloted Aircraft (BRASIL, 2015). Therefore, it is evident the importance of safe and agile communication, which requires a communications network that allows for the exchange of data in real time to enable the fulfillment of missions with greater efficiency.

CONCLUSIONS

A doctrinal change is currently underway in the Brazilian Army, as a result of the disruptive technological innovation brought by the AVTM-300 Tactical Cruise Missile, within the scope of the Astros 2020 Program. In this process, the military is an active pole and promoter of technological innovation. Such innovation brings with it the potential for disruption not only by the demand for doctrinal change, but also by the creation of a new organizational structure: the Artillery Command at Santa Barbara Fort. The challenge of creating this structure requires definitions about the chain of command for the use of the TCM and the subordination of the organization, an open debate at present. Given the inexistence, so far, of an official employment doctrine for this type of system (TCM), studies on the subject in the country have become crucial.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Since doctrinal change processes tend to be slow and intricate, it is necessary to put collective efforts towards the effectiveness of the TCM; therefore, it is necessary to
2. ensure continuity to the Brazilian Army's doctrinal change process, since it is essential for the Force's absorption of technological innovations, in order to avoid the mere "grafting" of new technologies onto obsolete doctrines; in this sense,
3. civil-military integration is seen as an important element for the maturation of the doctrine of employment of new weapons. The implementation of the Triple Helix (University, Armed Forces and Industry) serves as a catalyzing element, ultimately giving military spending an investment-based development model.

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